

HYDRODYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF A SPIRAL PUMP DRIVEN BY A WATER WHEEL UNDER LOW-HEAD OPEN CHANNEL FLOW CONDITIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20780537>

Abstract. *This study investigates the hydraulic performance of a water wheel driven spiral pump operating under low-head open channel flow conditions. The effects of water wheel diameter, flow velocity, and lifting head on discharge characteristics were analyzed using analytical and empirical methods. The obtained results showed that the discharge decreased exponentially from 0.108 m³/s to 0.013 m³/s when the lifting head increased from 0.5 m to 10 m. In addition, increasing the wheel diameter from 0.5 m to 2.0 m increased the discharge from 0.026 m³/s to 0.190 m³/s. The obtained fitting models demonstrated high accuracy with determination coefficients of $R^2 = 0.997$ and $R^2 = 1.000$. The results confirmed that optimal selection of wheel diameter and flow parameters significantly improves the efficiency of spiral pumping systems for irrigation applications in remote areas without electricity supply.*

Keywords: *water wheel, spiral pump, low-head, flow, low-head, flow parameters.*

1. Introduction

Today, the efficient use of water resources, the development of energy-saving technologies, and the creation of water lifting systems that do not depend on electricity are among the most pressing scientific and practical problems in the world. As a result of population growth, expansion of agricultural areas, and climate change, the demand for irrigation systems is increasing sharply. Especially in areas far from electricity networks, the use of traditional electric pumps to lift water requires high operating costs. Therefore, interest in hydraulic pumping systems that use the kinetic energy of natural water flows is growing [1-9].

In world practice, small hydropower and mechanical water lifting systems have been used for many years. In particular, spiral pumps (spiral pump or coil pump) and hydromechanical systems based on water wheels are distinguished by their ability to operate without electricity, simplicity of design, and low operating costs [1,2]. These technologies began to develop at the end of the 19th century, initially based on the concept of the Wirtz spiral pump. Later, spiral pipe systems were integrated with water wheels, allowing the kinetic energy of the water flow to be directly converted into mechanical rotational energy. As a result, environmentally friendly and autonomous systems for lifting water to a certain height appeared [2].

In recent years, scientific research on water lifting technologies based on renewable energy sources has increased significantly. According to international studies, pumping systems consume 20-22% of the world's electricity. In some industrial and irrigation systems, this figure

reaches 30-50%. Therefore, the development of alternative hydromechanical devices that reduce energy consumption is considered one of the priority areas in the energy and irrigation sectors. Spiral pumps are considered a promising technology, especially in small irrigation systems, foothill areas, open canals and agricultural facilities with limited electricity supply.

In Uzbekistan, rational use of water resources and increasing energy efficiency are important directions of state policy. A large part of the irrigated land in the republic is supplied with water through pumping stations, which leads to a large amount of electricity consumption. Especially in regions with dense irrigation networks, such as the Fergana Valley, there are opportunities to use the kinetic energy of open channel flows, which makes the introduction of spiral pumping systems operating on the basis of a natural energy source an urgent issue [4-9].

Although the current scientific works on spiral pump systems mainly present constructive solutions, general operating principles and experimental results, the influence of water wheel parameters on the pressure-flow characteristics of the pump has not been studied in depth enough. In particular, the issues of mathematical modeling of the dependence between wheel diameter, water flow velocity, wetted cross-sectional area and useful power are still relevant.

The main objective of this study is to analyze the hydrodynamic and energy parameters of a spiral pump system operating in low-pressure natural water flows, to determine the effect of water wheel dimensions on water consumption and head, and to develop a mathematical model of the system. During the study, the dependences between water flow velocity, water flow, wheel diameter, and useful power are analyzed, and recommendations are developed to improve the energy efficiency of the spiral pump system.

Literature review

Spiral pump systems, which use the kinetic energy of low-pressure water flows to lift water upward, have been widely studied as an energy-efficient irrigation technology in recent years. Spiral pumps are a promising device for small irrigation systems due to their ability to operate without electricity, their simplicity of design, and their low operating costs.

Müller [1,12] studied the hydraulic efficiency of water wheels and found that the water flow velocity and wheel diameter significantly affect the torque of the device. According to the results of the study, an increase in the diameter of the water wheel increases the level of utilization of flow energy. However, this work did not consider the process of lifting water through a spiral pipe.

Senior et al. [2] have experimentally analyzed the performance of conventional water wheels. They have shown that the water flow velocity and impeller geometry directly affect the useful work coefficient. Although the mechanical energy generation characteristics of the water wheel are studied in the study, a hydrodynamic model of the integrated systems with a volute pump is not developed.

Fraenkel [10] analyzed non-electric water lifting devices and noted that spiral pumps are an effective technology for agricultural water supply. The author pointed out that the main advantage of spiral pumps is the use of natural water flow energy. However, the dependence between spiral pipe diameter and water flow has not been analyzed in depth.

Williams [13] studied the energy balance in hydraulic machines and investigated the dependence between water flow and head, but did not provide practical parameters for volute pump systems operating in open channel flows.

Patil et al. [14] have reported that spiral tube water wheel pump systems are a low-cost technology for irrigation systems. The study shows that water can be lifted upward by rotating a

spiral tube using a water wheel. However, the dependence between water wheel diameter, flow velocity, and water flow is not well-established mathematically.

Tschiersch and Bohórquez [16] experimentally investigated the effect of spiral pump geometry on water lifting efficiency. The results showed that water flow increased with increasing spiral pipe diameter and rotation frequency. However, the study was conducted in a laboratory setting and did not consider natural open channel flow conditions.

Author	Research direction	Main result	Methodological approach
Muller [1,12]	Water wheel design and efficiency	Wheel diameter and flow velocity have been found to affect efficiency	Empirical and experimental hydraulic analysis
Senior et al. [2]	Hydraulic operation of traditional water wheels	The effect of flow velocity and blade geometry on η has been determined.	Experimental hydrodynamic analysis
Fraenkel [10]	Water lifting devices without electricity	Spiral pumps have been shown to be an effective technology for irrigation	Feasibility and design analysis
Williams [13]	Energy balance in hydraulic machines	The energy equation between water flow and pressure is based on	Analytical and energetic modeling
Patil et al. [14]	Spiral tube water wheel pump system	The convenience of the spiral pump for irrigation is shown	Theoretical and review approach
Tschiersch and Bohórquez [16]	Spiral pump geometry and efficiency	The effect of spiral pipe diameter and rotation frequency on water flow has been determined.	Laboratory experiments and mathematical analysis

The analyzed literature shows that the general design and operating principle of spiral pumps have been sufficiently studied in existing scientific works. However, the issues of comprehensive analysis of the pressure-flow characteristics of a spiral pump based on the parameters of the water wheel in low-pressure natural water flows, mathematical modeling of the dependence between water flow velocity, wheel diameter and lift height have not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, in this study, the working process of a spiral pump is analyzed using theoretical and analytical methods based on the parameters of the water wheel.

2. Materials and Methods

The object of the study was a spiral pump-water wheel system operating in a low-pressure open channel water flow. The study analyzed the process of converting the kinetic energy of the water flow into mechanical rotational energy through a water wheel and lifting water to a certain height using a spiral pipe.

Experimental studies were performed in open channel conditions. Channel flow parameters were varied in the following ranges:

1. Water flow velocity: $V = 0.5 - 1.5 \text{ m/s}$;
2. Water depth: $d = 0.2 - 0.5 \text{ m}$;
3. Water wheel diameter: $D = 0.5 - 2.0 \text{ m}$;

4. Lifting height: $H = 0.5 - 10$ m.

Q water flow, P_u useful power, n rotation frequency, η hydraulic efficiency, and H lifting height were taken as the main parameters of the system.

The main parameters are water flow velocity v , water flow Q , wheel diameter D , and lift height H .

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the principle of operation of a spiral pump.

This figure (1) shows a spiral pump system that uses open channel flow energy. The water flow rotates the impeller, which in turn pushes water up through the spiral pipe. The figure shows the flow velocity (V), water flow (Q), impeller diameter (D), and head (H) as the main parameters.

The water wheel is the main driving element of a spiral pump. It converts the kinetic energy of the water flow into mechanical rotational energy, ensuring the movement of water inside the spiral pipe [15]. The efficiency of the wheel depends on the water velocity, flow velocity, wheel dimensions and design parameters [10,14].

1 - Water wheel, 2 - Blades, 3 - Central shaft, 4 - Spiral coil pipe, 5 - Inlet section, 6 - Outlet section, 7 - Supporting frame, 8 - Coupling element

Figure 2. The main structural elements of a scroll pump.

Figure 2 shows the main elements of a spiral pump system, including the water wheel, central shaft, spiral pipe, water inlet and outlet points, and air chamber [16].

Hydraulic calculation methodology: determination of open channel flow velocity.

The velocity of water flow is determined using the velocity-distance method, which measures the time it takes to travel a certain distance:

$$V = \frac{L}{t} \quad (1)$$

where: V is the water flow velocity, m/s; L is the measured distance, m; t is the time, s. According to the measurement result, the average water flow velocity is $V = 0.896$ m/s.

The cross-sectional area of a water wheel directly in contact with the water flow is defined as follows [7], [8]:

$$A = d \cdot w \quad (2)$$

where: A - wetted cross-sectional area, m^2 ; d - water depth in the wheel, m; w - wheel width, m. The experimental setup is as follows: $d = 0.3$ m; $w = 0.6$ m.

Determining the kinetic energy of a water flow

The water wheel input power depends on the density, wetted cross-sectional area, and flow velocity and is determined by the following expression [13,15]:

$$P_{in} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot V^3 \quad (3)$$

where: P_{in} - water wheel input power, W; ρ - water density, kg/m^3 ; A - wetted cross-sectional area, m^2 ; V - flow velocity, m/s.

The angular velocity of the water wheel was determined based on the following empirical dependence with the flow velocity:

$$\omega = \frac{2V}{D} \quad (4)$$

here: ω -angular velocity, rad/s; V -flow velocity, m/s; D -water wheel diameter, m.

The rotation frequency is:

$$n = \frac{60\omega}{2\pi} \quad (5)$$

where n is the rotation frequency (rpm).

Only a fraction of the total power produced by the water wheel is converted into useful mechanical power. The efficiency is assumed to be $\eta = 0.4$ [7], [8]. Then:

$$P_{out} = \eta \cdot P_{in} \quad (6)$$

The useful pump power is related to water flow and lift height as follows:

$$P_{out} = \rho \cdot g \cdot Q \cdot H \quad (7)$$

$$Q = \frac{P_{out}}{\rho \cdot g \cdot H} \quad (8)$$

Where: ρ - water density, kg/m^3 ; g - acceleration of gravity, m/s^2 ; Q - water flow, m^3/s ; H - pressure or head, m. P_{out} - useful power, W;

Pressure-flow for spiral pump description The diagram shows that the water flow decreases with increasing head of the spiral pump. According to the results, the flow decreases sharply in the range of 0.5-3 m, and the decrease is relatively slow in the range of 3-10 m.

In order to assess the performance of a spiral pump, the dependence between pressure and water flow was analyzed.

Calculations have shown that the flow is directly proportional to the flow velocity. This dependence is defined by the following expression:

$$Q = A \cdot V \quad (9)$$

where: A is the wetted cross-sectional area of the stream (m^2), V is the flow velocity (m/s), Q is the water flow (m^3/s).

As the water flow velocity increases, the amount of water entering the volute pump increases, which directly affects the overall efficiency of the system.

The power coming from the water flow to the water wheel is:

$$P_{in} = \frac{1}{2} \rho \cdot A \cdot V^3 \quad (10)$$

The useful power of the water wheel and the spiral pump is:

$$P_u = \eta_t \cdot P_{in} \quad (11)$$

A mathematical model based on energy balance was used to evaluate the efficiency of the spiral pump based on the water wheel parameters. The kinetic energy of the water flow is converted into mechanical energy by the water wheel and is used to lift the water to a certain height using the spiral pump. On this basis, the following expression was obtained for the system:

$$Q = \frac{\eta_t \cdot A \cdot V^3}{2 \cdot g \cdot H} \quad (12)$$

Now, if the flow-contacting surface of a water wheel is assumed to depend on the diameter: A

$$A = b \cdot \lambda \cdot D \quad (13)$$

where: b - wheel width, m D - wheel diameter, m λ - wheel immersion ratio. If this surface is related to the wheel diameter, then the dependence of the flow on the diameter is:

$$Q = \frac{\eta_t \cdot b \cdot \lambda \cdot D \cdot V^3}{2 \cdot g \cdot H} \quad (14)$$

In many cases it is considered: $b = \mu \cdot D$

$$Q = \frac{\eta_t \cdot \mu \cdot \lambda \cdot D^2 \cdot V^3}{2 \cdot g \cdot H}; \quad Q = k \cdot D^2; \quad k = \frac{\eta_t \cdot \mu \cdot \lambda \cdot V^3}{2 \cdot g \cdot H} \quad (15)$$

Regression and empirical analysis methods were used to assess the effect of water wheel diameter on water flow. Based on the results, the following empirical dependence was obtained:

$$Q = a \cdot D^2 + b \cdot D + c \quad (16)$$

The pressure-flow characteristic of the scroll pump was analyzed based on the exponential decay model:

$$Q = Q_0 \cdot e^{-k \cdot H} \quad (17)$$

$$y = A \cdot e^{-kt} = 6 \cdot e^{-0.6t}$$

t

(18)

where Q_0 - initial water flow, k - empirical reduction coefficient, H - lifting height

The coefficient of determination, R^2 root mean square error (RMSE), and relative error (δ) indicators were used to assess the level of model fit.

The coefficient of determination was calculated using the following formula:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum(y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (19)$$

where: y_i - experimental values; \hat{y}_i - values obtained by the model; \bar{y} - average value

The mean square error was determined by the following expression:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (20)$$

The relative error was estimated as follows:

$$\delta = \frac{|y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{y_i} \cdot 100\% \quad (21)$$

Based on the results obtained, the optimal operating range of the spiral pump system and the effect of water wheel parameters on water flow and head were evaluated.

3.Results and Discussion

The study analyzed the hydraulic and energy parameters of a spiral pump system operating in low-pressure water flows. The calculations revealed that the water flow velocity, water wheel diameter, and head significantly affect the efficiency of the spiral pump.

According to the calculation results, it was observed that the water flow decreased with the increase in the pressure of the spiral pump. The results obtained were expressed in the following sequence. (See Figures 3-6)

Figure 3. Pressure-flow characteristics of a scroll pump

Figure 4. Dependence between water flow velocity and water flow

Figure 5. Dependence between water wheel diameter and water flow

Figure 6. Efficiency pressure values Dependence between

Figure 7. Dependence between water flow, water wheel diameter and flow velocity

Pressure-flow characteristic

The $H - Q$ pressure-flow characteristic of the spiral pump was analyzed based on the dependence. According to the results, water flow decreases with increasing head (Fig-1). An exponential regression model expressed this dependence:

$$Q = 0.1169e^{-0.2231H}$$

The coefficient of determination for this model is:

$$R^2 = 0.997$$

is equal to , which indicates a high agreement of the model with the calculated values. Therefore, as the head in a spiral pump increases, the hydraulic resistance increases, and as a result, the water flow decreases.

Velocity-flow dependence

The effect of water flow velocity on water flow $V - Q$ was evaluated using a graph. The calculation results showed that water flow is directly proportional to the flow velocity:

$$Q = 0.1800 \cdot V$$

Here, the 0.1800 value represents the wetted cross-sectional area of the flow. The regression result is

$$R^2 = 1$$

Water wheel diameter-flow dependence

The effect of water wheel diameter on water flow was analyzed based on polynomial regression. The resulting fitting equation was as follows:

$$Q = 0.0400D^2 + 0.0100D + 0.0110$$

For this:

$$R^2 = 1$$

The results show that water flow increases according to a quadratic law with increasing water wheel diameter. This is explained by the fact that the surface area interacting with water and the rotational torque increase with increasing wheel diameter.

Efficiency analysis

The system efficiency was evaluated depending on the head. The results showed that the highest efficiency was observed at low and medium pressure values. As the head increases, the hydraulic losses in the spiral pipe increase and the system efficiency decreases.

The regression model obtained for efficiency is:

$$\eta = 0.0000 \cdot H^2 - 0.0485 \cdot H + 0.7076$$

For this:

$$R^2 = 0.958$$

was established.

To evaluate the comprehensive performance of the spiral pump system, the dependence between water flow, water wheel diameter, and flow velocity was analyzed graphically. The model was expressed by the following empirical equation

$$Q = 0.045D^2 \cdot V$$

This dependence shows that water flow is linearly related to flow velocity and quadratically related to water wheel diameter. Therefore, in order to increase the efficiency of

the system, it is important to choose not only the flow velocity but also the optimal wheel diameter.

The results show that the efficiency of the spiral pump-water wheel system depends on three main factors: water flow velocity, wheel diameter and head. An increase in water flow velocity increases water flow, and an increase in diameter increases the torque. However, an increase in head reduces water flow. Therefore, when designing the system, it is necessary to optimize the parameters, and together. By optimally selecting the water wheel diameter and flow velocity, the system efficiency can be significantly increased. The results of this research serve as a scientific basis for optimizing and implementing spiral pump systems.

4. Conclusion

The study demonstrated that the hydraulic performance of the spiral pump strongly depends on lifting head, flow velocity, and water wheel diameter. The obtained results showed that increasing the lifting head from 0.5 m to 10 m reduced the discharge from 0.108 m³/s to 0.013 m³/s due to hydraulic losses inside the spiral pipe. Meanwhile, increasing the water wheel diameter from 0.5 m to 2.0 m increased the discharge approximately seven times. The developed empirical and regression models showed high agreement with the calculated data ($R^2 = 0.997-1.000$). The proposed spiral pump system can be effectively applied for low-head irrigation and water lifting systems operating without electrical energy.

REFERENCES

1. Müller, G. (2009). Simplified design of water wheels for developing countries. *Journal of Hydraulic Research*, 47(5), 630-636.
2. Senior, J., Müller, G., & De Cesare, G. (2010). Hydraulic performance of traditional water wheels. *Journal of Hydraulic Research*, 48(2), 225-232.
3. Paish, O. (2002). Small hydro power: Technology and current status. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 6(6), 537-556.
4. Urishev, O., Ersin, A., Metin, G., & Kuvondikov, Q. (2026). ESTIMATING ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION OF PUMPING PLANTS IN IRRIGATION SYSTEMS. *Innovation Science and Technology*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18472643>
5. SALOMOV, OK, & URISHEV, O. (2025). IMPORTANCE OF HYDROELECTRIC STATIONS AT GLOBAL AND NATIONAL LEVELS AND DEVELOPMENT DIRECTIONS. “UZBEKHYDROENERGETICS” scientific and technical journal, 7(2), 17-28.
6. Urishev, O., Salomov, U., Ergashev, S., Kuchkarov, A., Madaliev, M., Abdukarimov, B., & Juraev, N. (2025). Efficiency assessment of micro hydropower for agriculture using modern modeling. In *BIO Web of Conferences* (Vol. 173, p. 03031). EDP Sciences. DOI:10.1051/bioconf/202517303031
7. Salomov, U., Kuchkarov, A., & Urishev, O. (2025). Analysis of the dependence Between Water Consumption and Heading in a Micro Hydropower System. *Journal of Construction and Engineering Technology*, 21-29. <https://doi.org/10.24412/2181-4473-2025.3.204>
8. Urishev, O., Salomov, U., & Shasha, C. (2024). Methods of Analysis and Assessment of the Economic Efficiency of Micro Hydropower. *Journal of Construction and Engineering Technology*, 2(2), 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12570514>

9. Og'Lee, UOM, & Og'Lee, RMF (2020). The fundamental elements of micro-hydropower stations. Science and Education, 1(2), 236-240.
10. Fraenkel, P. (1986). Water lifting devices. Intermediate Technology Publications, London.
11. Kiebel, P. (2008). Powering the countryside: The economics of micro-hydropower. *Renewable Energy*, 33(11), 2439-2444.
12. Müller, G., & Wolter, C. (2004). The breastshot waterwheel: Design and performance. *Proceedings of the ICE - Engineering Sustainability*, 157(4), 203-211.
13. Williams, AA (1997). Pumps as turbines: A user's guide. Intermediate Technology Publications.
14. Patil, SH, Sutar, SG, Mirage, SR, Patil, AM, & Nangre Patil, BH (nd). A review paper on spiral tube water wheel pump. Adarsh Institute of Technology & Research Centre, India.
15. Patil, SH, Sutar, SG, Mirage, SR, Patil, AM, & Nangre Patil, BH (nd). A review paper on spiral tube water wheel pump. Department of Mechanical Engineering, Adarsh Institute of Technology & Research Centre, Vita, India.
16. Tschiersch, Kim & Bohórquez, O.. (2019). Coil pump design as an object of meaningful learning. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. 1161. 012027. 10.1088/1742-6596/1161/1/012027.
17. Juraboev, I., Jurakulov, S., Urishev, O., Rakhmatov, O., Eshkobilov, O., Sadirova, K., & Aliyarova, L. (2025). Improving Thermal Performance of Solar PTC Using Internal Finned Structure. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 661, p. 04018). EDP Sciences.<https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202566104018>
18. Akramova, S., Urishev, O., Mamurov, B., Nurmanov, S., Apakhodjaeva, T., Irmukhamedova, L., & Gaimnazarov, K. (2025). CFD Modeling of Latent Heat Storage with Cylindrical PCM Capsules. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 661, p. 04010). EDP Sciences.<https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202566104010>